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Veda and the social life of women: A thorough study

Dr. Moumita Bhattacharya¹

Abstract

The study of Indian culture has fascinated many scholars, because of its unity in diversity and complexity. Indian culture is one of the longest surviving cultures in the world, because of its quality of resilience and inclusiveness. India is a land with an ancient culture and heritage, which has a continuous tradition from ancient period. Many facts of Indian culture and heritage of later age are almost based upon the culture of the Vedas which are particularly and remarkably true for the Hindu society and culture. Vedic culture was very rich in its various aspects like religion, political, social ideals and philosophical thoughts. The patriarchal family was the basic unit of Vedic society. A family is an important unit for making a whole society. If every family in a society becomes happy and prosperous then the whole society also will be exalted in welfare. For this reason, the Vedic period seers thought that it a better to obtain welfare for a family at first. The Vedic period people tried to make good family and to keep it well-disciplined at first for the welfare of whole society. There is a moral for the welfare of family that charity begins at home and then endeavor for the welfare of the whole society. In the house or other domestic fields, the bride was given greatest importance as if the welfare of the family depends upon her conduct and activities. For the benefit of the society, one should develop her good qualities and moral ethic values. In this way an individual, a family and the whole society can achieve welfare.

Vedic Culture

The vedic culture of India is one of the few, longest surviving culture in the world, because of its quality of resilience and

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inclusiveness. The study of Indian culture has fascinated many scholars, because of its unity in diversity and complexity. Many historians accept that India is a land with an ancient heritage, going as far back as third millennium B.C. and has a continuous tradition from ancient period. Of course knowledge of this ancient society has a continuous tradition from ancient period. Of course knowledge of this ancient society has been clouded with various theories being put forth by different authorities.

Although it was wealthy in all respects, the encounter with many outside cultures came to India have helped to enrich it. The German scholar like Max Muller popularized the idea of the origin in India of the Aryan speaking people. The initial theories about the Aryan people mainly derived from the science of comparative philology and those today stand corrected on the basis of the recent sciences of paleontology, archeology and linguistics.

The discoveries of the Indus civilization, that began as recently as the 1920s, also reversed the earlier notions of the Aryan origin in India. Vedic civilization was very rich in its various aspects like religion, philosophy, political ideas and social ideals but the archeological evidences for the Vedic civilization is not remarkable. It was enriched with its literature in the form of Mantras, Brahmanas, Aranyakas and Upanishads. These are the main sources of information about the Vedic age. In fact the poetical talent and beauty as revealed in the Vedic literature deserve appreciation even in the eye of this modern period. Apart from this, other aspects of this civilization also are to be ignored. The Vedic literature can be called the fountain- head of all facets of Indian civilization.

The Rigveda contains a variety of cultural materials including political, social, religions, secular and spiritual. It bears a reliable picture of gradual development of ancient Indian society and many aspects of its culture. Many facts of Indian culture of later age are almost based upon the culture of the Vedas, which are particularly and remarkably true for the Hindu culture and indirectly for other religions like, Buddhism and Jainism. Hence it is said that ‘Vedo Khila-Dharmamulam.’ According to Prof. A. B. Arnold “the Rigveda is not a book, but rather a library and a literature, the collected remains of the work of many centuries”.

Vedic people were with a mixed pastoral and agriculture economy in which cattle-rearing played a predominant role. Cattle formed their most valued possession and the chief form of their wealth; a wealthy person was called 'gomat'. Prayers were offered for the increase in cattle population. The sacrificial priest was rewarded for his services with cattle and the cow was the chief medium of exchange. As might be expected of people without cities, the early Aryans did not have an advanced technology. But they certainly enjoyed an advantageous position in relation to their adversaries. They used horses and chariots, which were not known to the pre-Vedic people.

The Rigveda mentions thirty clans and tribes; five of them were major ones and referred to as Panchajana. Kingship was the same as tribal chiefship, the term 'Rajan' being used for the tribal chief. Primarily a military leader, the chief of the tribe fought for the cows and not for territory. He ruled over his people (=Jana). He was therefore called their protector (gopa janasya or gopati janasya). The term 'Gopati', basically indicating the protector of the herds of cattle, came to acquire the extended meaning of the protector of the people or tribe (jana). Yet the idea of territorial monarchy emerged towards the close of the Rigvedic period when the chief/king (rajan) came to be looked upon as an upholder of the Rashtra.

The basic unit of Vedic society was the patriarchal family called the Kula. The eldest male member of the family was known as the Kulapa (Protector of the family). In the hymns desire is expressed for praja, including both boys and girls. But the people seem to have been keen on having brave sons (Suvirah) who could fight their wars. In spite of the patriarchal character of the family, the position of women seems to have been in some respects in Rigvedic period than in subsequent time.

Women in Vedic Culture

Women the key to basic principles of Sanatana-dharma in the traditions of Vedic society of India have played an important role in conservation and maintenance of our culture. Throughout the many years of Vedic culture, women have always been given the highest level of respect and freedom, but also protection and safety. Women are usually the first inspiration and first teacher of our children.

In the Vedas, when a woman is invited into the family through marriage, she enters “as a river enters the sea” and “to rule there along with her husband, as a queen, over the other members of the family” (Atharva-Veda 14.1.43-44). Many of the great men who had become powerful proponents of Sanatana-dharma also had strong and inspiring mothers or wives. In this world we need people to help in all levels of life to protect the Vedic knowledge and traditions, and women have a very important part to play. This honor towards women should be maintained today by the preservation of genuine Vedic culture, either in the country or in the institutions, which has always been a part of India.

There is a Vedic saying, “Where women are worshiped, there the gods dwell” and where the women are happy, there will be prosperity. Furthermore, the direct quotes from the Manu Samhita explain as follows: “Women must be honored and adorned by their fathers, husbands, and brothers-in-law, who desire their own welfare. Where women are honored, there the gods are pleased; but where they are not honored, no sacred rite yields rewards. Where the female relations live in grief, the family soon wholly perishes; but that family where the family relations live in grief, the family soon wholly perishes; but that family where they are not unhappy ever prospers. The houses on which female relations, not being duly honored, pronounce a curse, perish completely, as if destroyed by magic. Hence men who seek (their own) welfare, should always honor women on holidays and festivals with (gifts of) ornaments, clothes and (dainty) food” (Manu Smriti III.55-59).

The institution of marriage seems to have been established. It was regarded very auspicious as a relation between husband and wife. Girls normally married after puberty. Some of them may have grown up and stayed for long as spinsters in their parental homes in unusual circumstances. Such was the case with Ghosa, for example, who was suffering from a skin disease and could get a husband only when the Ashvins befriended her. In some cases, a woman could freely mix with young men. She could take part in sacrifices with her husband. Some unmarried women like Visvavara and Apala, however, performed rituals all by themselves, though often with the purpose of finding husbands.

Beautiful ideas regarding this are found expressed in a Sukta of the Rigveda. Best wishes are expressed in following way there-

Sumangaliriyam badhurimam Sameta pasyeta.

Soubhagyamasyai dattvyathatastam vi paretana.

Here the badhu or bride has been described as Sumangali. In the house or other domestic fields the bride was given greatest importance as if the welfare of the family depends upon her conduct and activities. She was expected to be the samrajni of all the members of the family to which she belongs. Such an expectation has been expressed in a very beautiful language in the Rigveda as follows-

Samrajni Svasure bhava Samrajnj Svasrvam bhava.

Nanandari Samrajni bhava Samrajni adhi Devrsu.

A family is an important unit for making a whole society. It can be said in other words that many families collectively make a society. So if every family in a particular society become happy and prosperous then the whole society also will be exalted in welfare. For this reason, the Vedic seers thought that it is better to obtain welfare for a family at first, when all the families will become prosperous and well-disciplined then the whole society will consequently be in welfare. So, the Vedic people tried to make good family and to keep it well-disciplined at first for the welfare of whole society. There is a saying/moral that charity begins at home, this is also like that. For the peace of the family, it is well said in the Atharvaveda as follows-

Anubratah pituh putro Matra bhavatu Sammanah.

Jaya patye Madhumatim vacam vadatu Santivam.

So, in the family a son should obey his mother and father a first and then endeavor for the welfare of the whole society. In the *Taittiriyaopanishad* also the Rishi advised as follows - Matrdevobhava, Pitrdevobhava Acarydevobhava etc. for the benefit of the society one should develop his good qualities. In this way an individual, a family and the whole society can achieve welfare. Such was the grand 'idea of the Vedic people and this can be followed even in our present-day society. It is quite natural that the members of a society can express their good will for the welfare in a beautiful Mantra as follows-

Samani va Akutih, Samana hradyani vah.

Samanamastu vo mano yatha voh susahsati.

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